

BINH DUONG UNIVERSITY

The International Conference Proceedings

**ENSURING THE RIGHTS
OF PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES
IN THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF VIET NAM
AND
OTHER COUNTRIES OF THE WORLD**

SOCIAL SCIENCES PUBLISHING HOUSE

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Human values of ensuring the protection of rights of persons with disabilities

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Abstract:

Disability is not a blot. This is a form of nature, and we should not discriminate against them. Without distinction or prejudice, a PwDs person shall be entitled to all the rights outlined in this Declaration. PwDs have the same fundamental rights irrespective of the cause, character, and severity of their handicaps and disabilities. PwDs have the same fundamental rights that all other people have. PwDs have a right to access the policies intended to help them become as independent as feasible. PwDs must be safeguarded from any exploitation and abuse that is discriminatory, abusive, or demeaning. There should be provisions for their representation everywhere accordingly. People with good human values will respect everyone without looking at their caste creed, colour, or disability.

In Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations have focused on legal and practical action that will be necessary to achieve the goals of social inclusion and sustainable development of PwDs, their rights, representation, and dignity, particularly in the areas of social policy and employment.

Keywords: “PwDs, Sustainable, Discrimination, Economic, Social Security, Equality, Representation”

1. Introduction

A person with a disability is a part of our family, society, or country, which cannot be ignored. For example, a car cannot move if one tire is a puncher. The same thing applies to countries worldwide. Society, family, or country cannot move smoothly without discrimination against PwDs, Dalits, and women. A family, society, and country can run smoothly if we establish such kinds of Laws and existing Laws to ensure equality, equal opportunity for work, and special representation for PwDs in the country. This new dimension will speed up any country's economy and society. According to this positive approach, the country will run speedily. The United Nations Charter, signed in 1945, is the international organisation's founding document. According to Article 55, the United Nations must work to provide the following circumstances of stability and well-being to foster peaceful and amicable relations among nations based on respect for the concept of equal rights and human self-determination.

- A. Higher living standards, full employment, and conditions for economic and social progress and development;
- B. Solutions to global issues relating to the economy, society, health, and education;
- C. Universal respect for and observance of fundamental freedoms for all without distinction based on race, sex, language, or religion [1].

The United Nations General Assembly issued a declaration on the rights of PwDs on December 9, 1975, known as the 'Declaration of the Rights of PwDs' as the 3447th resolution overall [2]. Without distinction or prejudice, a PwDs person shall be entitled to all the rights outlined in this Declaration.

Independent of the cause, character, and severity of their handicaps and disabilities, PwDs have the same fundamental rights as others. PwDs are entitled to the same civil and political rights as everyone else. PwDs have a right to policies that help them be independent in all respects.

The right to economic and social security for PwDs includes finding and keeping a job, engaging in a useful, fruitful, and well-paying vocation, and joining unions based on their talents. The right to live with one's family or with foster parents and participate in all social, creative, and recreational

activities is guaranteed to PwDs. PwDs must be safeguarded from exploitation and abuse that are discriminatory, abusive, or demeaning.

2. Who is a Person's Disability

The Declaration defines anyone “who lacks physical or mental capacities and is unable to provide for the needs of a normal individual or social life”.

A prohibition against discrimination that extends the rights to all PwDs, regardless of their race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinions, national or social origin, state of wealth, birth, or other circumstances.

So, a ‘person disabilities’ means any person unable to ensure by himself or herself, wholly or partly, the necessities of a normal individual and/or social life as a result of deficiency, either congenital or not, in his or her physical or mental capabilities.

2.1 Definition of Disability

A disability is an impairment that can affect one or more of the following areas: cognition, growth, intelligence, activity, ability, sensory, or some combination of these. It may be present by birth or develop throughout a person's lifetime and significantly impacts their daily activities. Disability is a contentious topic, having various definitions attached to it by various societies. It can relate to physical or mental traits that certain organisations, especially those in medicine, see as having to be repaired. It can reference the restrictions placed on individuals by the ablest society. PwDs have the same health requirements as people without impairments for things like cancer screenings and vaccines.

2.2. United Nations Summit

At a historic United Nations summit in 2015, world leaders endorsed the Seventeen Sustainable Development Goals of the 2030 United Nations Agenda for Sustainable Development, which came into force in 2016. Although the objectives are not legally enforceable, each state's responsibility is to design them. Providing updates on own sustainable development policies and how to implement them. Social inclusion and respect for the rights of PwDs are important elements of sustainable development. So, the States, after the ratification of the United Nations Convention and explore the two paths (i) that the states have adopted to improve the status of PwDs and (ii) that help the country to implement the Sustainable Development Goals. A number of measures were identified and focused on legal and practical action that will be necessary to achieve the goals of social inclusion and sustainable development of PwDs, particularly in social policy and employment. While the objectives of sustainable goals are not legally enforceable, each state is responsible for designing its sustainable development policies for PwDs and providing updates on how they are being put into active action. On the other hand, it should also represent them in all fields.

3. Social Inclusion and Disability

A socially inclusive society shows the health of its citizens and society. Social inclusion and recognising PwDs' rights and representation fit into the larger picture of sustainable development. A better opportunity will allow them to flourish and lead a dignified life in modern society. The state shall provide a healthy environment for their development without any discrimination. It is also the state's responsibility to provide them with a good working environment for growth. The state has established strict rules and laws and ensures equality and non-discrimination. It should establish policies for their upliftment and representation in all kinds of opportunities.

3.1. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities

The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities is an international human rights treaty of the United Nations that aims to “protect the rights and dignity of PwDs. The object of the Convention is to promote, protect and ensure the full enjoyment of PwDs and to provide an ideal environment for full equality and enjoyment under the law”. In the Charter of the United Nations, it is declared that the “inherent dignity and values and equal and inalienable rights of all members of the human family are the foundation of freedom, justice, and peace in the world”. Similarly, the UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights will make a “significant contribution to addressing the profound social disadvantages of PwDs and promoting their participation in the civil, political, economic, social, and cultural spheres with equal opportunities in both”. All the developing and developed countries have to ensure the application of the Convention on the “Rights of PwDs deals with matters such as general principles based on which the rights of PwDs are to be promoted and protected, and the obligations undertaken by the state to adopt them.

This Convention focuses on the situation in the Republic of Macedonia following its ratification of the UN Convention, examines a few of the steps taken to improve the situation of PwDs there, and supports the obligation of the nation to carry out sustainable development goals. It is required to fulfil the objectives of sustainable development, particularly in social policy and employment, and it will be helpful for the social inclusion of PwDs.

Being mindful of the commitment made by the Member States to work together and separately in support of the organisation to advance improved living standards, complete employment, and conditions for economic and social growth and development, reaffirming its belief in human rights and fundamental freedoms as well as the Charter's declarations of social justice, peace, and human dignity.

3.2. Universal Declaration of Humans 1975

Recalling the principles of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenants on Human Rights, the Declaration of the Rights of the Child, and the Declaration on the Rights of Mentally Retarded Persons, as well as the standards already set for social progress in the constitutions, conventions, recommendations, and resolutions of the International Labour Organisation, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, the World Health Organization, the United Nations Children's Fund and other organisations concerned,

4. The special Instrument on the Rights of PwDs

Recalling also Economic and Social Council resolution 1921 (LVIII) of May 6, 1975, on the prevention of disability and the rehabilitation of PwDs, it emphasises that the Declaration on Social Progress and Development has proclaimed the necessity of protecting the rights and assuring the welfare and rehabilitation of the physically and mentally disadvantaged. It is necessary to prevent physical and mental disabilities and assist PwDs to develop their abilities in the most varied fields of activities and promote their integration as far as possible into normal life.

A few developing countries with limited resources can devote only limited efforts to achieving the Declaration on the Rights of PwDs and calls for national and international action to ensure that it will be used as a common basis and frame of reference for the protection of these rights.

PwDs shall enjoy all the rights outlined in this Declaration. Paragraph 7 of the Declaration on the Rights of Mentally Retarded Persons applies to any possible limitation or suppression of those rights for mentally PwDs. They are entitled to the measures designed to enable them to become as self-reliant as possible.

4.1. PwDs and Right to Health

They have the right to medical, psychological, and functional treatment, including prosthetic and orthotic appliances, to medical and social rehabilitation, education, vocational training and rehabilitation, aided counselling, placement services, and other services which will enable them to develop their capabilities and skills to the maximum and will hasten the processes of their social integration or reintegration. They have the right to economic and social security and decent living [3].

4.2. PwDs and Right of Freedom

Recognising that in order for PwDs to fully enjoy all of their human rights and basic freedoms, they must be able to access the physical, social, economic, and cultural environment, as well as health, education, information, communication, that is ensured by all government for their citizens [4].

4.3. PwDs and Right of Representation and Intolerance Worldwide

PwDs can fully enjoy all their human rights and basic rights. Disability is not based on any caste, race, colour, creed, or gender, but everyone has the right to equality. This right is based on something other than citizenship, which must be addressed based on citizenship to PwDs at the airport of any country. If you apply for admission or a job form in any international university, you are asked in one column whether you need any disability representation. The representation of PwDs and no discrimination will be intolerant worldwide.

5. Policy Activism on a National and International Basis

Some developed countries have tried providing rights, equality, and equal work opportunities to PwDs. Such as Sweden, Switzerland, and many European countries have followed these treaties seriously. When we talk about developing and under-developed countries, we need to think of the efforts of these countries better. These countries suffer from poverty, unemployment, hunger, and other problems [5]. The countries which have signed on Treaty are working in that direction. Common Wealth Countries introduced the Rights of the PwDs Act around 2016, which binds the state government and the central government to the rights of PwDs.

5.1. Abolish discrimination on the basis of disability

After India signed and ratified the United Nations CRPD (UNCRPD) in 2007, the process of enacting new legislation in place of the PwDs Act, 1995 (PwDs Act, 1995) began in 2010 to make it compliant with the UNCRPD. The Act lays stress on non-discrimination, full and effective participation and inclusion in society, respect for difference and acceptance of disabilities as part of human diversity and humanity, equality of opportunity, accessibility, equality between men and women, respect for the evolving capacities of children with disabilities, and respect for the right of children with disabilities to preserve their identities. After a series of consultation meetings and a drafting process, the rights of persons with disabilities act, 2016 [6] (RPWDS Act, 2016) was passed by both houses of Parliament. It was notified on December 28 2016, after receiving the presidential assent.

Indian Constitution provides for abolishing discrimination on the basis of disability. To prevent discrimination in the country, the Constitution of India in Articles 15 and 16 states, “No one shall be discriminated based on sex, colour, caste, creed, and religion [7]”. Extending this line of thinking, the RPWDS Act 2016 envisages the concept of non-discrimination. It provides an excellent elaboration of the constitutional guarantee by considering the circumstances of PwDs. Section 3, Equality and non-discrimination, guarantees access without discrimination [8], and Section 20, Non-discrimination in employment- prohibits discrimination when an employee acquires a disability during service. It also prevents denial of promotion to the next higher post on the basis of disability [9].

Every person, including PwDs, has his life and liberty guaranteed under Article 21 of the Constitution [10]. There can be no traffic in human beings (including PwDs), and beggars and other forms of

forced labour are prohibited, and the same is made punishable in accordance with law (Article 23) [11].

5.2. Political Representations for PwDs

The demand for representation for PwDs in India was raised in the Parliament on September 30, 2013, in Bhubaneswar. A group of PwDs demanded 4% representation/reservation for PwDs in Parliament and other institutions of democracy. Justifying the demand for a quota of 22 Lok Sabha seats and 10 Rajya Sabha seats for PwDs, Jitendra Kumar Biswal said that across the social spectrum, such people, who are backward in the way of representation/reservation for SC, ST, and OBC in India, are eligible for representation. “Although there is the representation for PwDs in the field of education and job opportunities, without political empowerment, the vision of an equal and inclusive India is not possible,” declares the launch of a nationwide and worldwide campaign for political empowerment of PwDs. Huye Biswal said that he would demand a reservation from Panchayats to Parliament. Such provisions should be made available to the governments at the earliest. Due to this PwDs also get a chance to join the mainstream. It is similar to the representation of black people in developed countries [12].

6. Human Values ensuring the Care of Person disabilities

There is a great need to increase valuable education among children by parents and teachers. We are witnessing increasing violent activities, behavioural disorders, and a lack of unity in society. Valuable education enables us to understand our needs and visualise our goals. For this, there is a need for changes in education and improved education status over time, and there is a need to indicate the right conditions and direction for their fulfilment. Multidisciplinary education is urgently and strictly needed to inculcate human values in the society of any country. Because of that good education, people will inculcate tolerance and tolerance in human values.

Which is an urgent need in today’s society and business world. They have many positive characteristics that create bonds of humanity among people and thus hold value for all human beings. Human values are the basis of any practical life within society. This basic education will end the discrimination against PwDs and give them respect. The followings are the basic human values for ensuring the dignity and life of a person with a disability.

- I. **Human Firstly** - The basic human value of society is to consider the person with a disability as a human being Firstly. This acceptance will change society's perspective and help reduce the miseries of PwDs. People should avoid labelling them as they are human and not “handicapped” or “disabled”.
- II. **Be a true Friend** - Every person needs a behaviour with empathy and a true friend who can understand the problems of a person with special needs. The service-providing agencies are working well by providing a human touch in the life of the person with a disability.
- III. **Provide Space for Expression** - PwDs reflexively make their way through the world. They want freedom of speech and workable conditions. PwDs are entitled to the full meaning of the right to free speech. The ability to communicate, in whatever form, must be available to every person with a disability.
- IV. **Accessible and Participative Environment** - One of the basic needs of a human being is to move freely to enjoy life and all the basic amenities available. A society shall provide an environment for active participation in community life.
- V. **Ensure Family Connection** - PwDs must ensure life continuity through family and neighbourhood connections. The society shall endeavour steps to eliminate barriers and

strengthen the evidence base for future public and private actions to reduce the impact of disability on individuals, families, and society. It became a success with the help of society and the Governments' efforts.

- VI. **Give Respect and Dignity** - PwDs must be treated with respect and dignity. Any account of human rights must begin with the moral right of all people to be treated with respect. For PwDs, it means that while preserving the moral value of the individual, interpreting the disability as a disorder would be an insult to human dignity. The principle of dignity requires that every person is taken to human dignity. It is a moral value and a means of dignity, which imparts a moral value in human behaviour.
- VII. **Ensure freedom to Live** - Every individual has to ensure the freedom of PwDs to enjoy and must have the freedom to choose how they want to live their lives and receive the support they need.
- VIII. **Freedom of Choice and Control of Life** - PwDs must be able to exercise choice and control in all areas of their lives.
- IX. **Accessible Home** - PwDs must be able to live in homes of their choice and choose the supports they need.
- X. **Protection of Employment** - PwDs must be able to enjoy the benefits of true productivity through employment and/or contributions as members of their communities

7. Future Directions and Suggestions

- I. PwDs community should demand benefits that are both just and necessary; We should remember that it is the collective responsibility of all to care for the handicapped; this will raise both the country and the society. It is everyone's main responsibility to benefit them like a family.
- II. The Firstly thing is that the state should ensure that the government should provide proper representation to them in the Firstly of all ratio.
- III. The government and NGOs need to recognise the voice of PwDs and raise issues.
- IV. There is a need to provide strong encouragement and support to mentally challenged people and their representatives to form organisations.
- V. There is a need to teach such courses in schools and colleges that remove discrimination against the handicapped.
- VI. There is a strong need to disseminate information in the regional language regarding disability, to reach far and wide across the country, and create awareness.
- VII. Change in the education curriculum has the potential to change the attitude of the professional.
- VIII. Disability services and benefits must be explained, appropriated, monitored, and disbursed.
- IX. The need to introduce health legislation, including reviewing existing legislation and planning amendments from time to time or introducing new laws from time to time.
- X. There is a need to do more and more research on the factors associated with
- XI. PwDs and mental disorders should get their proper representation. They should also get equal societal rights and contribute shoulder-to-shoulder to the country's progress.

8. Conclusions

After that effort, have PwDs fully entered the mainstream? All the countries in the world have overcome all kinds of barriers to economic, political, and social inclusion they have historically faced.

The inclusion of PwDs is a complex and multifaceted topic, and different aspects of inclusion overlap and influence one another.

People should be sensitised to PwDs from a religious viewpoint, and this sensitivity must be raised to that level. Where they would accept that it is their religious duty to accept these PwDs as it is because of nature or due to an accident. One must be convinced him /herself by where he treated such people not to be treated as PwDs, but as persons differently abled. If this can be achieved, then only the people would start accepting the such person as their kith and kin then only such a person would lead a life in our society like any other normal person. All country's governments should work hard on the representation of differently-abled persons.

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